

Svetlana **BUZU**

gr. did. I, Liceul Teoretic M. Viteazul din Chișinău

Collaborative Learning vs. School Success

CZU 373.091 | doi.org

Abstract: Collaborative learning involves the combined intellectual effort of students or students and teachers together, where students work in groups of two or more, looking for mutual understanding by completing a task together, finding solutions or meanings, or creating a product. Although collaborative learning takes different forms and is practiced by teachers from different disciplines and teaching traditions, the area is linked by a number of important assumptions about learners and the learning process. The aim of this article is to clarify the difference between individual learning and collaborative learning in order to highlight the opportunities the latter provides for school success.

Keywords: collaborative learning, individual learning, classroom techniques, student-centered approach, peer teaching.

Rezumat: Învățarea prin colaborare implică efortul intelectual al elevilor și al profesorilor în crearea unui produs, în găsirea unor soluții prin lucru în grup. Deși ia diferite forme și este practică de profesori la diferite discipline prin diverse tradiții de predare, această formă de învățare are la bază o serie de ipoteze importante despre elevi și procesul de învățare.

Mariana **BESCHIERU**

gr. did. sup., Liceul Teoretic M. Eminescu din Chișinău

Scopul acestui articol este de a stabili diferența dintre învățarea individuală și învățarea prin colaborare, pentru a evidenția oportunitățile oferite de aceasta din urmă în vederea asigurării un demers la clasă de succes.

Cuvinte-cheie: *învățare prin colaborare, învățare individuală, metode de predare, abordare centrată pe elev, învățare de la egal la egal.*

*“Coming together is the beginning.
Keeping together is progress.
Working together is success.”
(Henry Ford)*

Collaborative learning is not merely a teaching method; it is a way to communicate with people in order to highlight the skills and contributions of individual group members. Moreover, for every single group action there is a division of authority and responsibility among the group members, which is the basic principle of collaborative learning. The main characteristics of collaborative learning are: a common task or activity; small group learning, co-operative behavior; interdependence; individual responsibility and accountability [7].

Developing interpersonal skills is just as important as learning on your own. Developing social skills in group work – learning to work together – is the key to quality group work. The students receive several learning tasks aimed at achieving academic and social qualifications. Many strategies involve role play within each small group (e.g., recording, providing incentives, summarizing) to ensure positive interdependence among group participants and to allow the students to practice different team skills [7].

Regular “group processing”, a “debriefing time” in which the students think about how they are doing, is built into the learning task so that groups can work more effectively in a learning environment [6]. Creating a collaborative classroom requires as much interest and ability as actually working in collaboration with others. Going out from the comfort zone and engaging students in group activities is hard work, especially at the beginning, but it has numerous benefits.

Collaborative learning can occur peer-to-peer or in larger groups. Peer learning or peer instruction is a type of collaborative learning that involves students working in pairs or small groups to discuss concepts or find solutions to problems.

Collaboration is a promising mode of human engagement that has become a 21st-century trend. The need to think together and work together on critical issues has increased [1], causing the stress to shift from individual attempts to team work and from autonomy to community [1]. As teachers we should prepare students for life by paying attention to the ways their competences are formed and developed. Luckily, the National Curriculum encourages collaborative learning by suggesting pro-

ducts like infographics, collages, posters, presentations, scrapbooks and lapbooks, cartoons and mind-mapping, talk-shows, dialogues, debates etc.

Collaborative learning is a social activity where the students learn to work with all types of people. During small-group interactions, they find many opportunities to reflect upon and reply to the diverse responses fellow learners bring to the questions raised. This exchange inevitably helps students to better understand other cultures and points of view. When questions are raised, different students will have a variety of responses. Also, students learn to relate to their peers and other learners as they work together in group enterprises. This can be especially helpful for students who find social skills acquisition difficult. They can benefit from structured interactions with others, which would actively involve them in learning.

For instance, our students and we participated in an international project Climate Action project which was a free student-centered project, a 6 weeks journey involving more than 2.5 million students across 135 countries, in the course of which students had to fulfill creative tasks. It was supported by governments in 15 countries. The project was free, student-centered and aimed to lead to a change of behavior through education. It was in collaboration with WWF and NASA, and endorsed by Jane Goodall, President Higgins, scientists and public figures. It was covered by media across 45 countries including BBC, CNN and National Geographic. During 6 weeks, students had to brainstorm, explore, create, discuss and share their findings in English online. Each week they created a video of their findings to be published on Climate Action project website. This way students were able to learn from their peers globally and discovered that climate change may appear very differently in other parts of the world. During the last week there were live, virtual interactions via video conferencing tools, so students were able to share their findings live. The organizer hosted experts during webinars so students were able to learn from world-renowned experts like Matt Larsen-Daw from WWF, Rick Davis from NASA, Celine Cousteau and others. Great excitement they had to meet students from Poland and Croatia via Zoom, this required a lot of work in group, preparing the presentation, questions. Each member had the opportunity to contribute and be apt to take more ownership of their material and think critically about related issues when they worked as a team (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Students' interaction in the International Project, Padlet

Another benefit is a psychological one, which reduces anxiety and frustration and boosts self-confidence and positive attitude toward teachers and peers. The motivation and confidence to participate are clearly important if these benefits are to emerge, as well as the interchanges that require question answering and explanation and are open to challenge and justification, which will require participants to assume a variety of functional roles [8]. Our students achieve all these qualities while working on digital projects, dialogues, common presentations, or debates. Since more exchanges take place among students in small groups, the students receive thus more personal feedback about their ideas and responses. This feedback is often not possible in large-group instruction, in which only one or two students would exchange ideas while the rest of the class listens. Advances in technology are making an increasing impact on educational curricula, learning materials, and instructional practice. Emphasis is placed on interactions as common understandings are negotiated and developed across differences of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Indeed, collaborative learning should thrive on these differences [8].

Although many restrictions were imposed on education due to the ongoing pandemic, technology has redesigned the idea of collaboration, creating a multitude of learning opportunities. Collaborative activities are effective synchronously, when students have to perform tasks in breakout rooms or using interactive whiteboards requiring common work, such as *MURAL*, *aww app*, *Padlet*, *Today's Meet* etc.

One of the aims of education is to improve students' academic performance, which is another benefit of

collaborative learning. Academic performance depends on many variables, such as intelligence, socioeconomic status, personal characteristics, attitudes, values, environment, teaching-learning techniques etc. The didactic methodologies employed in the classroom improve and influence student performance. In order to optimize educational opportunities we need to be aware of the relationship between a specific teaching method and academic performance, and of how collaborative and individual learning affects academic performance – specifically, in our case, in English classes – so that the students' academic performance is improved.

Since students are actively involved in interacting with each other on a regular basis in an instruction-led mode, they become able to understand their differences and learn how to resolve the social relationship problems that may arise [6]. Collaborative learning encourages the students' natural tendency to socialize with their peers – on a professional level. Students often have communication difficulties outside of class. Openings can be exploited in order to lead to a discussion of these problems between the teacher and the student in a nonthreatening way, while additional support from other student services units in such areas can be a beneficial by-product [11]. From our experience, besides knowledge, the students acquire a number of skills, such as digital skills, communicative skills, and critical thinking. Both teachers and students are enthusiastic when using *Tricider*, *storyjumper*, *jamboard*, *sway*, *AnswerGarden* etc.

Collaborative learning activities lead to the development of high level thinking skills [12]. The students are indeed actively involved in learning. Their working

together represents the most effective form of learning interaction. When students work in pairs, one person listens while the other partner discusses the question they are working on. Both are developing valuable problem-solving skills by formulating their ideas, discussing them, receiving immediate feedback, and responding to questions and comments [6].

In order to develop critical thinking skills, students need a base of information to work from. Acquiring this base often demands some degree of repetition and memory work. When this is accomplished individually, the process can be tedious, boring, or overwhelming. However, when students work together, the learning process becomes more interesting and enthusiastic. Students are trained to be ready to complete the tasks and work together within their groups, and they must understand the subject that they plan to contribute with to their group. They are also given time to process group behaviors, such as checking with each other to make sure homework assignments are not only completed, but understood. These interactions help students learn self-management techniques. Our younger students experience all this when creating scrapbooks and lapbooks, while the older ones prefer creating infographics in *Canva* or *Piktochart*.

Collaborative learning provides the teacher with many opportunities to observe students interacting, explaining their reasoning, asking questions, and discussing their ideas and concepts [12]. These assessment methods are far more conclusive than reliance on written exams alone [4]. D. W. Johnson states: "In a learning situation, student goal achievements are positively correlated; students perceive that they can reach learning goals if and only if the other students in the learning group also reach their goals" [6]. Thus, students seek outcomes that are beneficial to all those with whom they are cooperatively linked. When individuals get stuck, they are more likely to give up, but groups are more likely to find ways to keep going. An advantage is that collaborative learning provides many opportunities for various forms of student assessment.

Through interaction with students during each class, the teacher gains a better understanding of each student's learning style and how they perform the tasks. Following this, teachers can plan further activities according to the peculiarities of each group. We may therefore assert that talk-shows, oral presentations, presenting cartoons, dialogues, debates etc. assess not only students' knowledge of English, but also develop other skills and competences.

Compared with competitive and individualistic efforts, collaborative learning has numerous benefits

and typically results in higher achievement and greater productivity, as well as more caring, supportive, and committed relationships; also better mental health, social competence, and self-esteem.

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